

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: This article discusses the phraseology, a subject of special linguistics using them in teaching English. Linguistics as a scientific discipline aims to study the interrelationship and interaction of language and culture. Science is a synthesis of culture and linguistics, and its formation goes back a long time. Science is a synthesis of culture and linguistics, and its formation goes back a long time.

Key words: paremiological units, paremia, linguoculturology, ethnolinguistics, orthology.

At the beginning of the 19th century, schools of linguistic and cultural studies were formed under the auspices of famous scientists such as N.D.Arutyunova, V.V.Vorobyov, V.I.Karasik, V.V.Krasnix, V.N.Telia¹. Over time, a certain conceptual-terminological tool of linguo-cultural studies is being formed using various research theories and methods of linguo-cultural analysis. One of the tasks of this science is to study the cultural, cognitive, and psychological characteristics of language and linguistic individuals representing different ethnic groups. In this regard, linguoculturology allows discovering the characteristics of the cultural values of the people.

Researcher V.V.Vorobyov² considers the science of linguocultural science “a complex scientific science of a synthesizing type that studies the relationship and interaction of culture and language in the activity and reflects this process as an integral structure of units in the unity of linguistic and extralinguistic content using systematic methods.”

¹ Арутюнова, Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка, событие, факт / Н.Д. Арутюнова. - М.: Наука, 1988. - 339 с.; Воробьев, В.В. Лингвокультурология / В.В. Воробьев. - М.: РУДН, 2008. - 336 с.; Карасик, В.И. О категориях лингвокультурологии / В.И. Карасик // Языковая личность: проблемы коммуникативной деятельности: сб. науч. трудов. - Волгоград: Перемена, 2001. - С. 3-16.; Красных, В.В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология: лекционный курс / В.В. Красных. - М.: Гнозис, 2002. - 284 с.; Телия, В.Н. Русская фразеология: семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологический аспекты / В.Н. Телия. - М.: Языки рус. культуры, 1996. - 288 с.

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Linguistics has become a field of scientific science with its own subject and object of study in the classification of humanities. Summarizing the acquired knowledge is important, which, on the one hand, arouses interest for the research model of the scientific object, and on the other hand, requires the formation of general and limiting criteria and characteristics of the studied concept. In our opinion, the concept of linguoculturology researcher V.V.Vorobyov is complete and meaningful, because he created researchers in the methodology of linguistic analysis called "systematic methods".

Based on the general integrative scheme “culture – language” according to V.V.Krasnykh. Other important features of the studied science are expressed in the definition: “Linguculturalology is a science that studies the manifestation, reflection and fixation of culture in language and speech. This is directly related to the study of the national landscape of the world, linguistic consciousness, and the characteristics of the psycho-linguistic complex.”³ Completely different objects of research - the national view of the world, specific cognitive features, linguistic consciousness are being formed.

It should be noted that the linguistic heritage of V.Humboldt⁴ opens new perspectives in the field of humanitarian knowledge. A combination of many factors of a linguistic and extralinguistic nature contributed to the emergence of linguoculturology as a scientific discipline. The decisive factor here is the revision of various methods in language learning aimed at increasing its functions, as well as in connection with worldview and national-centered tasks.

Lingvokulturology has an important interdisciplinary character, it combines various humanitarian knowledge. At present, such researches in related disciplines are most in demand in linguistics. Linguistics as a systematic and diverse scientific discipline interacts with many disciplines: cognitive linguistics, linguistic philosophy, national linguistics, cultural studies, national psycholinguistics, etc.

Lingvokulturology is presented as an integral part of national culture, as one of the components of ethnolinguistics, which is studied in the synchronous order of

³ Красных, В.В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология: лекционный курс / В.В. Красных. - М.: Гнозис, 2002. - 284 с.

⁴ Гумбольдт, В. Избранные труды по языкознанию / В. Гумбольдт. - М.: Прогресс, 2000. - 400 с.

language and culture. According to the researcher N.F.Alefirenko⁵, language culture is an integral part of any ethnic culture, it is a synergistic combination of interrelated phenomena of culture and language, strengthened and mastered by a certain ethno-linguistic consciousness (combination, synthesis, collection).

Language is the most important tool for understanding the spiritual culture of an individual and the entire nation, an important part of ethnic culture. The uniqueness of each linguistic consciousness implies a certain prism through which a person understands and perceives the world, as well as the spiritual culture of the people. Based on the specific characteristics of the manifestation of geographical, historical and social characteristics of each ethnic group, the world landscape is characterized by a certain cultural and national identity, which is established against the background of the unity of the perception of the world.

Academician Y.D.Apresyan⁶ describes in detail the modern image of the linguistic landscape of the world. In his opinion, each language contains a certain character of a person and his way of perceiving the world. The definitions expressed in it become a system of unique views, a unique social philosophy. The language-specific way of conceptualizing reality is partly multifunctional and ethnic in nature, and therefore allows speakers of different languages to see the world slightly differently due to the diversity of their native languages. On the other hand, this method is “simple” and most of the main components differ from the scientific linguistic picture of the world.

“Modern linguistics combines the history of the language (diachronic) and its current state (synchronic), in which the language system and language norms (orthology) are thoroughly and comprehensively studied. In this norm and linguistics lies the idea of a diverse and multidimensional structure of language, each level of which is carefully studied by separate linguistic disciplines. It is similar to names such as phonetics, morphemics, lexicology (the science that studies the vocabulary level), morphology, syntax. In recent years, linguistics has also included the highest level of interest - text. Each level (except phonetics) has formal and substantive plans.

⁵ Алефиренко, Н.Ф. Лингвокультурологическое содержание понятия «дискурс» в современной когнитивной лингвистике / Н.Ф. Алефиренко // Русское слово в мировой культуре: материалы X Конгресса Международной ассоциации преподавателей русского языка и литературы. - СПб., 2003. - Т. 1. - С. 9-19.

⁶ Апресян, Ю.Д. Образ человека по данным языка: попытка системного описания / Ю.Д. Апресян // Вопросы языкознания. - 1995. - № 1. - С. 37-67.

Linguistics, in addition to the study of specific languages, also deals with the general principles of language activity, comparison of languages, their kinship and typological relations.”

Linguistics reveals cultural information that is a necessary component of society. It exists in stable language forms that include phraseological and paremiological units that are part of linguistics.

Phraseology is a subject of special linguistics, which began to form in Russian linguistics from the 40s. 20th century, and in the West it has not yet been divided into a separate department of linguistics. Parimiology as a subject of linguistics and not folklore analysis attracted attention only at the end of the 20th century. A detailed study of paremiological units has become an object in local and world linguistics.

The word *paremia* is Greek and means “proverb”, but researchers also include proverbs in this concept. Researcher L.B.Savenkova⁷, under the term paremiological unit, we mean “secondary linguistic signs - closed static phrases (proverbs and proverbs) that are a sign of the relationship between the situation or reality.”

The linguist V.A.Voropaeva⁸ identifies paremies and words in the Holy Scriptures for this category and describes them as having “identity marks”. G.L.Permjakov⁹ emphasized the paremiological indicator of language in proverbs. Permjakov, who made a great contribution to science in defining the differences between proverbs and words, classifies proverbs as follows. In his work, the author notes that proverbs and proverbs are grammatically complete wisdom, and it is necessary to interpret them more widely. Let's look at the classification of paremias presented by the researcher:

1. “Alphabetical classification. This requires that the proverbs be arranged alphabetically according to the initials of the first word.
2. Classification by reference words (also lexical or encyclopedic) implies the division of proverbs according to the main words that make up this proverb.

⁷ Савенкова, Л.Б. Русская паремиология: семантический и лингвокультурологический аспекты / Л.Б. Савенкова. - Ростов н/Д.: Изд-во Рост. ун-та, 2002. - 240 с. 11

⁸ Воропаева, В.А. Сопоставительная характеристика английских, немецких и русских паремий и фразеологизмов, выражающих толерантность: дис. ... канд. филол. наук: 10.02.20 / Виктория Александровна Воропаева. - Тамбов, 2007. - 168 с

⁹ Пермяков, Г.Л. От поговорки до сказки: (заметки об общей теории клише) / Г.Л. Пермяков. - М.: Наука, 1970. - 239 с.

3. Monographic classification is based on the grouping of proverbs according to the place or time of collection, according to the collector.

4. Genetic classification divides material according to its origin, in particular, according to the languages and peoples that gave birth to it.

5. Thematic classification includes the distribution of proverbs according to the topics of the statement, that is, according to their content”¹⁰

Thus, the linguistic overview (brief information) and analysis of the actual issues of defining the term *paremia* in English (American), Uzbek and world philology allows making a number of conclusions. As can be seen from the above rules of the term *paremia* proposed by researchers, the question (issue) of what *paremia* means remains open, there is no universally recognized single rule of the term of this species. The analysis of the etymology of the word *Paremia* shows that it is mainly related to symbolic stories that perform a moral or instructive task. As a philological (linguistic) term, it began to be used in its current sense later.

Today, there is no definition of a proverb that would give integrity to such a verbal organization, where each sign is related to a single goal and direction. But the above definitions allow us to get a general definition, which shows the ambiguity and versatility of the interpretation of the proverb definition. Following the researchers, we believe that proverbs are folk proverbs, concise, clear thought depth and power, stable, figurative, artistically and rhythmically structured sentences in colloquial speech.

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¹⁰ Пермяков, Г.Л. Пословицы и поговорки народов Востока / Г.Л. Пермяков. - М.: Лабиринт, 2001. - 624 с.

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